

SMILE PLEASE!

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Smile, smile, smile please!
Smiling you should never cease!
Smile brings you Love and Peace!
Smile, smile, please!
Smile gives you beauty-Smile makes you mighty!
Smile is the wonderful gift given by Almighty!
Smile brings you warmth-Smile gives you strength!
Smile helps you walk through the life's labyrinth!
Smile is the finest lip guard you can ever apply
Smile is the lasting wealth you can forever supply!
Smile is the brightest jewel you can always wear!
Smile is the greatest marvel you can forever share!
Smile keeps you active after day's hard work!
Smile throws the light when the path looks dark!
Smile gives you hope when everything is lost!
Smile gives a better future burying the past!
Smile takes all the worries out of your heart!
Smile makes you healthy, gentle and smart!